

IMPORTANCE OF LEARNING ENGLISH NOWADAYS

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Abstract

The article discusses the importance and necessity of English language around the world. English is the greatest common language. Additionally, this language can help people in every sphere, because English is the most used and understandable almost for everybody, so learning and knowing it so vital that can open any doors.

Keywords: English, greatest common language, major window of the modern world, British Empire,

Introduction

Language is significant source of our life that separates us from animals, and makes us human. There are lots of languages in each country that people speak and understand each other. Currently, English is the primary language of not only countries actively touched by British imperialism but also many business and cultural spheres dominated by those countries. As such, it is a useful and even necessary language to know. Learning English is important and people all over the world decide to study it is a second language. Many countries include English as a second language in their school syllabus and children start learning English at a young age. English is the language in science of aviation, computers, diplomacy and tourism. Knowing English increases your chances of getting good job in a multinational company. In today's global world, English is so vital that can understand almost all people around the world. At the same time, to learn this requires lots of affords.

The emergence of English as a World language is now indisputable. Crystal (2000) and Nunan (2001), as well as British Council (2013), argued that the spread of English provided unlimited access to modern world of science, information and communications technology (ICT), money, power, international communication, and intercultural understanding as well as entertainment and may more fields. English has been said to have official status in 60 countries as the second language and has a prime place In 20 more TEFLON International Conference 2,pp.253-260,2015,Undayana University, Bali Page 254 countries as the primary foreign language (Yang,2001).It is widely recognized that English is

the native language of five countries: the United States, the United Kingdom, Australia, New Zealand, and Canada. (Ratha Rintaningrum,2015)[253-260]

Besides that, English also increases intelligence, because we learn a language that is not our native language, which is the growth of our brain intelligence, especially for children. For children, this is an excellent stimulus for them to learn English as a foreign language in its golden age (HAKIM & CHIANYI, 2019). In addition to educating the brain, learning English also makes it easier for us to have relationships because we can easily communicate with strangers.

HISTORICAL BACKGROUND OF ENGLISH

English was initially the language of England, but over the historical efforts of the British Empire, it has developed the primary or secondary language of numerous former British colonies such as United States, Canada, Australia, Sri Lanka, and India. Currently, English is the primary language of not only countries actively touched by British imperialism, but also many business and cultural spheres dominated by those countries. In another word even outside of countries like the U.S and U.K, many people can speak and understand English. It is the language of Hollywood and the language of international banking and business. As such, it is a useful and even necessary language to know. An estimated 1 billion people worldwide speak English On top of this, 67 countries have English as their official language and 27 countries have English as their secondary official language. It has to do with history and the key is the British Empire.

EDUCATION

English is also necessary for the field of education. More information is given in this language that shows how it can open the doors in education. Mostly, English is the dominant business language and it has become almost a necessity for people to speak English if they are entering a global workforce. Research from all over the world shows that cross-border business communication is most often conducted in English and many international companies expect employees to be fluent in English.

ENGLISH IS THE INTERNET LANGUAGE

English is the most used language online, with nearly 1 billion users typing and chatting in this. If you can speak and read English you will be able to access and enjoy more resources online you can read world news, participate in a discussion on a forum. In short, learning English will open a whole world of entertainment for you.

It is hard to imagine a young person nowadays who does not speak or study at least one language besides their mother tongue. Globalization forces so many people to communicate and cooperate more in a variety of business.

But every language is important. It depends on the situation, you need a world language to communicate with people around the world without learning their regional language. English is the world language and it helps you everywhere.

English is also hugely important as an international language and plays an important part even in countries where the UK has historically had little influence.

1. English gives you access to multiple cultures

Good knowledge of English will allow you to access films, music, and literature from hundreds of countries around the globe.

2. With English, you can study all over the world

Since English is spoken in so many different countries thousands of schools and universities around the world offer programmes in English.

3. English is the language of the media industry

Because of the prominence of Hollywood in global media, an enormous amount of films, TV shows, and popular songs are written in English.

4. It helps to understand other language

English has a long and fascinating history that spans wars, invasions, and influences from around the globe. Cultures that have helped shape modern English include the Romans, Vikings, and French. For this reason, it's a hybrid language comprised of Latin, Germanic, and Romance elements.

5. Travelling is a lot easier with a good knowledge of English

Imagine you are a Spanish person on holiday in Thailand, while your hotel receptionist might not be able to answer your question in Spanish. They will likely be able to answer your question in English.

Conclusion

English is one of the most used and dominating languages in the world. Undoubtedly, English plays an important role in each sphere like in education, business, politics, and technology. Although learning English can be challenging and time-consuming, it can create many opportunities and be valuable to learn.

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